

Metal Complexes of some Peptide Derivatives. Part-V. Complex Formation of Copper(II) with *N*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)- methylsuccinamic Acid and *N*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)methyl- maleimic Acid. Influence of Adjacent C=C Bond on Proton-Ligand and Metal-Ligand Equilibria with Amide Moiety

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Equilibrium study on the complex formation of Cu^{II} with *N*-(2-benzimidazolyl)-methylsuccinamic acid, BzNHCOCH₂CH₂COOH (hereafter, BSA or LH) and *N*-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylmaleimic acid, BzNHCOCH=CHCOOH (hereafter, BMA or LH₂) (where, Bz=2-benzimidazolylmethyl moiety), provided evidence of formation of complexes of the types, Cu(H₂L)(H₂O)₂; Cu(HL)(L)(H₂O)₂, Cu(H₂L)(OH)(H₂O)₂ with BSA and Cu(L)(H₂O)₂, Cu(L)(OH)₂ and Cu(L)₂⁻ with BMA. Proton-ligand and Cu^{II}-ligand constants determined by pH-metric method at 30° in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium, I=0.2 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) were correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands, labilisation of the amide (NHCO) proton in BMA by the adjacent C=C bond and intramolecular hydrophobic interaction.

INTERACTION of transition metal ions with simple amino acid and small peptides have been the subject of considerable study in recent times, since many of these *in vitro* systems served as models for the otherwise complex *in vivo* metal-protein interactions playing vital roles in the enzymatic processes. Protonation and metallation at the amide carbonyl oxygen atom is the general feature of interaction of the neutral amide (NHCO) group¹. Metallation at the amide nitrogen atom is possible only through substitution of the amide proton, for which the presence of a primary ligating site suitable for formation of 5- or 6-membered chelate ring involving the metal ion, is however essential^{1,2}. With a view to see the effect of an adjacent C=C moiety on the proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria involving the amide bond, two structurally related typical amide derivatives, viz. *N*-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylsuccinamic acid (hereafter, BSA, I) and

N-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylmaleimic acid (hereafter, BMA, II) have been selected for study.

The present paper describes the results of an equilibrium study on the complex formation of BSA and BMA with Cu^{II} at 30° in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium, I=0.2 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃).

Experimental

Ligands BSA and BMA: The ligand BMA was prepared by condensing maleic anhydride with 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole³ in chloroform medium, following the reported procedure⁴. The ligand BSA was obtained similarly by condensing succinic anhydride with 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole. Both BMA and BSA, obtained as shiny white crystalline solids after recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol, were air-dried and gave satisfactory analysis for C, H, N and equivalent weight (pH-metric): BMA, m.p. 160°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 280 (N-H), 1 710 (COOH), 1 660 (C=C) and 1 640, 1 450, 1 350 cm⁻¹ (amide I, II, III); BSA, m.p. 220°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 340 (NH), 1 720 (COOH) and 1 650, 1 450, 1 360 cm⁻¹ (amide I, II, III). All other reagents were of AnalaR grade and the solutions for pH-metric study were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water and purified ethanol⁵.

The experimental procedure for equilibrium study was similar to our earlier work⁷. pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter (accuracy $\pm$ 0.01 pH) employing a special glass

electrode in conjunction with an SCE. Analytical hydrogen ion concentrations were calculated by using corrections^{8,9} for mixed solvent and ionic product of water¹⁰, $pK_w = 13.83$ at 30°. A representative set of pH-titration data are presented in Fig 1. Formation constants (Table 1) were evaluated by using the computer programme SCOGS¹¹ with the aid of a IBM 1130 computer at the Department of Computer Science, University of Calcutta.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves of BSA and BMA in absence and presence of Cu^{II} in rate at 30° in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, $I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3): (1) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (2) (1) + 0.001 M Cu^{II} nitrate, (3) (1) + 0.01 M (BSAH^+) (NO_3^-), (4) (2) + 0.01 M (BSAH^+) (NO_3^-), (5) (1) + 0.01 M (BMAH^+) (NO_3^-), (6) (2) + 0.01 M (BMAH^+) (NO_3^-); Initial volume of each solution = 50 ml, titrant = 0.125 M NaOH.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria: BSAH^+ titrated as a biprotic acid, LH_2^+ , while BMAH^+ titrated as a triprotic acid, LH_3^+ (Fig. 1). Closeness of the first step deprotonation constant ($K_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$) of BSAH^+ and ($K_{\text{LH}_3}^{\text{H}}$) of BMAH^+ to those of succinic acid¹² and maleic acid¹³ respectively, suggested release of proton from the carboxylic functions. Comparable values of the second step deprotonation constants, viz. K_{LH}^{H} for BSAH^+ and $K_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$ for BMAH^+ , with the deprotonation constant of the benzimidazolium cation¹⁴ indicated the release of N_3^{H} proton of the benzimidazolium moiety of these two ligands in the second step deprotonation. The release of the third proton from BMAH^+ , therefore, must

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND Cu^{II} -LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH BSA AND BMA

Temp. = 30°, Aqueous ethanol medium = 50% (v/v), Ionic strength $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

BSA		BMA	
$pK_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$	4.55	$pK_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$	3.20
$pK_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}$	5.70	$pK_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$	4.20
$\log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{LH}_2}^{\text{2H}}$	-6.74	$pK_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}$	7.20
$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_-, \text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{H}}$	-4.54	$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})}^{\text{H}}$	-5.01
$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_-, \text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{H}}$	6.54	$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})}^{\text{Cu}}$	5.08
$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_-, \text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{Cu}}$	3.51	$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{OH})}^{\text{Cu}}$	-1.46
$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_-, \text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{Cu}}$	-1.04	$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})}^{\text{Cu}}$	4.80
$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_-, \text{L})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})}^{\text{Cu}}$	-7.58	$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})}^{\text{Cu}}$	9.38
$pK_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{H}} = 5.94$; $pK_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{OH}} = 12.00$		$\log K_{\text{I}}$	9.96

have taken place from the amide group. Though the amide group is known to remain neutral¹ almost in the entire pH range in absence of transition metal ions, the C=C double bond adjacent to the amide moiety in BMA by virtue of its vacant π^* anti-bonding molecular orbitals probably polarised the amide group to such an extent as to release the amide proton even at neutral pH. Though the possibility of enolisation eqm. (1) of the amide moiety (III, IV)

could not be ruled out, the successive deprotonation of BMAH^+ (or, LH_3^+) could be represented by eqms. (2-4) and those of BSAH^+ (or, LH_2^+) could be represented similarly by eqms. (2) and (3) as shown in Scheme 1.

Cu^{II} -BSA equilibria: Buffer region corresponding to the complexation equilibria of BSAH^+ with Cu^{II} was observed at pH values slightly lower than that corresponding to the deprotonation of the COOH and the N_3^{H} benzimidazolium moieties of the ligand and overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of $\text{Cu}^{\text{2+}}$ (aq.) ions (Fig. 1).

Three mole of proton per mole of Cu^{II} were released giving an inflection point with appearance of turbidity. The plot of $\bar{n}$ (average number of protons released¹⁵ per metal) against pH showed two distinct portions: $0 < \bar{n} < 2$ (pH 3-5) and $2 < \bar{n} < 3$ (pH 5-7) indicating two reaction steps, of which the initial step involved the release of two protons per Cu^{II} followed by another step involving the release of one proton per Cu^{II} .

Scheme 1. Proton-ligand equilibria with BMA.

Release of three protons per Cu^{II} implied deprotonation of COOH , amide and N_5^{H} protons during complexation. Terdentate ($\bar{\text{O}}, \bar{\text{N}}, \text{N}$) chelation of Cu^{II} by the carboxylate oxygen atom, amide deprotonated N-peptide atom and N_5 benzimidazole atom, was not feasible due to the involvement of a 7-membered chelate ring. Terdentate ($\text{O}, \text{O}, \text{N}$) chelation by the carboxylate oxygen, amide carbonyl oxygen and N_5 benzimidazole atom, or bidentate ($\bar{\text{O}}, \bar{\text{N}}$) chelation by carboxylate oxygen atom and amide deprotonated N peptide atom could neither release three protons per Cu^{II} nor these were feasible for stereochemical reasons. The only possible mode of coordination leading to the release of two protons in the initial step and one more in the following step, therefore, should be bidentate ($\text{N}, \bar{\text{N}}$) chelation of Cu^{II} by the N_5 benzimidazole atom and the amide deprotonated N peptide atom involving the release of N_5^{H} benzimidazolium proton and the amide proton to form the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ followed by deprotonation of the uncoordinated COOH group of the ligand H_{-1}LH^- ion in this 1:1 Cu-ligand complex according to eqms. (5) and (6), respectively,

Charges are omitted from the expressions for clarity. Here, the ligand species H_{-1}LH^- and $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{2-}$ in the complexes stand for the ions $\text{Bz}\bar{\text{N}}\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$ and $\text{Bz}\bar{\text{N}}\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$, respectively. The bidentate ($\text{N}, \bar{\text{N}}$) chelated complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})$ would take up two molecules of solvent water as ligand due to inherent tendency¹⁸ of Cu^{II} to have a square-planar geometry. This gave rise to the possibility of formation of hydroxo complexes through deprotonation of coordinated water according to eqm. (7),

Therefore, in calculating the formation constants (Table 1), the species, LH_3^+ , LH_2^+ , LH , L^- ; Cu^{2+} , $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$; $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ were considered to exist in the complexation equilibria.

Species distribution curves for the Cu^{II} -BSA system (Fig. 2) showed that nearly 80% of total Cu^{II} was present in the form of the complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ at pH 6.0-6.5, where the concentrations of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ were less than 10%. The predominant Cu^{II} containing species in the region of biological pH were the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (60%) and the hydroxo species $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ (40%). The hydroxo complex

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -BSA system: (1) LH_3^+ (2) LH_2^+ , F_L , L^- ; F_M , Cu^{2+} , (3) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (4) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (5) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, (6) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, (7) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$.

$\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ made its first appearance at $\text{pH} \geq 7$.

Deprotonation constant, $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{H}}$ of the uncoordinated COOH group in the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ ions was quite close to that

($K_{H_2L}^H$) of the free ligand. Deprotonation constant, $K_{Cu(H_{-1}L)(H_2O)_2}^H$ of the complex $Cu(H_{-1}L)(H_2O)_2$ was found to be quite close to that of equatorially coordinated water molecules in square-planar complexes of Cu^{II} ^{7,17}. These further supported the assumption of non-involvement of COOH group in coordination.

Cu²⁺ - BMA equilibria: Non-involvement of the COOH group of the ligand BMAH⁺ (LH₂⁺) ion in the complexation equilibria with Cu^{II} was indicated by the occurrence of its deprotonation (eqm. 2) in the same pH range in the absence and in the presence of Cu^{II} ions (Fig. 1). The carboxylate deprotonated zwitterionic species, LH₂[±], was the predominant ligand species in the pH range of complex formation. The buffer region corresponding to the deprotonation of N₃H (eqm. 3) and -NHCO- moieties (eqm. 4) were observed at lower pH values in presence of Cu^{II} with release of four protons per Cu^{II} , indicating thereby the successive formation of bidentate (N, N̄) chelated Cu^{II} complexes Cu(L) and Cu(L)₂²⁻ through substitution of the benzimidazolium (N₃H) and the amide protons of the ligand LH₂[±] according to eqms. (8) and (9).

As the buffer region corresponding to these complexation equilibria was close to that corresponding to the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu^{2+} (aq.) ions (Fig. 1), the formation of the hydroxo species $Cu(OH)^+$ and $Cu(OH)_2$ were taken into consideration in calculating the stability constants of metal-ligand complexes. Formation of a ternary complex species, $Cu(L)(OH)^-$ were assumed to accommodate the possibility of deprotonation (eqm. 10) of coordinated water in the $Cu(L)$ complex which was likely to take up one or two molecules of solvent water at the requirement of square-planar geometry¹⁶ for Cu^{II} .

Therefore, the species, LH₂[±], LH⁻, L²⁻; Cu^{2+} , $Cu(OH)^+$, $Cu(OH)_2$, $Cu(L)$, $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ and $Cu(L)(OH)^-$ were considered to exist in the complexation equilibria.

The species distribution curves (Fig. 3) of the Cu^{II} -BMA system showed that in the region of biological pH, the predominant Cu^{II} containing species were $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ (≈70%); $Cu(L)(OH)^-$ (≈25%) and $Cu(OH)_2$ (≈5%). The complexes $Cu(L)$ and $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ were formed to the maximum extents at pH 5 (62%) and 6.75 (80%), respectively. Deprotonation constant, $K_{Cu(L)}^H$ of the $Cu(L)$ complex was found to be quite close to that of equatorially coordinated water in square-planar complexes^{7,17} of Cu^{II} .

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -BMA system: (1) LH_2^+ , (2) $LH_2^{\pm}$, (3) LH^- , F_M , Cu^{2+} , (4) $Cu(OH)^+$, (5) $Cu(OH)_2$, (6) $Cu(L)$, (7) $Cu(L)(OH)^-$, (8) $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$.

Modes of bonding of ligands BSA and BMA with Cu^{2+} : In spite of apparent similarity in the modes of bonding offered by the ligand $H_{-1}LH^-$ ion in the BSA complex, $Cu(H_{-1}LH)(H_2O)_2^+$, with that by the L^{2-} ion in the BMA complex $Cu(L)$, stability constant (K_{CuL}^{Cu}) of the Cu^{II} -BMA complex was found to be nearly 40 times higher than the stability constant ($K_{Cu(H_{-1}LH)(H_2O)_2}^{Cu}$) of the Cu^{II} -BSA complex. Such higher stability of Cu^{II} -BMA complex indicated definite participation of the C=C double bond of the coordinated ligand (L^{2-}) ion in metal-ligand bonding in some way or other. Terdentate modes of bonding (IX or X) involving direct association of the C=C bond with Cu^{II} to form some sort of a $Cu^{2+} \dots L^{2-} \pi$ -bond would though reduce flexibility of the ligand but still appeared to be more favourable for the Cu^{II} -BMA complex due to higher entropy of chelation over the (N, N̄) bidentate mode of bonding (XI), which was the only possible mode for the Cu^{II} -BSA complex. Coplanar disposition of ligand sites as in IX would be favoured over the alternate mode (X) due to the inherent tendency of Cu^{II} (d^9) to have a square-planar geometry¹⁶. Comparable magnitude of the deprotonation constant $K_{Cu(L)}^H$ of coordinated water in the Cu^{II} -BMA complex to that of the equatorially coordinated water in typically square-planar complexes^{7,17} of Cu^{II} further supported the square-planar structure (IX). The $Cu(L)$ complex, therefore, would exist as $Cu(L)(H_2O)$ in solution. Stacking of the ethylinic moiety over the aromatic π -system of benzimidazole ring of the coordinated ligand in the 1:1 Cu -BMA complex $Cu(L)(H_2O)$ could not occur, as that would destroy the planarity of the complex and resonance of the peptide bond¹. None of the above stabilising interactions were, however, possible in the (N, N̄) bidentate chelated 1:1 Cu -BSA complexes (XI).

The $\log K_{CuL}^{Cu} / K_{Cu(L)_2}^{Cu(L)}$ value (0.78) for the Cu^{II} - BMA complexes was much lower than the statistically expected value (≈ 1.6) for terdentate chelation¹⁸ to form an octahedral $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ complex. The observed value was, however, close to but little higher than the statistically expected value (≈ 0.60) for bidentate chelation to form a square-planar Cu^{II} complex. Therefore, terdentate chelated structure (IX or X) of $Cu(L)$ complex must have undergone a structural change to provide scope for the formation of $(N, \bar{N})$ bidentate chelated $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ complex. Such a structural change in going from $Cu(L)$ complex to $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ complex was probably responsible for slightly higher value of $\log (K_{Cu(L)}^{Cu} / K_{Cu(L)_2}^{Cu(L)})$. There is scope for further stabilisation of the bidentate chelated square-planar $Cu(N, \bar{N})_2$ geometry of $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$ complex through stacking (XII) of the ethylinic moiety of one coordinated (L^{2-}) ligand over the aromatic π -system of the second (L^{2-}) ligand, while still retaining the planarity of the $Cu(N, \bar{N})_2$ moiety without rupturing the peptide bond resonance and leading to the isomeric equilibria^{20,21} of the type (11) between the open (op.) and closed (cl.) forms

(Et stands for ethylinic moiety) (11)

of the complex $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$. The isomeric equilibrium constant (K_I) as defined by,

$$K_I = [Cu(L)_2^{2-}]_{cl.} / [Cu(L)_2^{2-}]_{op.} \quad (12)$$

is concentration-independent and hence dimensionless. A high value of K_I would indicate the predominance of the (cl.) isomer having intramolecular hydrophobic interaction (XII) while a small value

of K_I would indicate the presence of the (op.)-isomer, devoid of such interaction in appreciable amounts. The value of K_I was calculated by assuming

$$K_{Cu(L)_2}^{Cu} / (expt.) = ([Cu(L)_2]_{op.} + [Cu(L)_2]_{cl.}) / ([Cu][L]) \quad (13)$$

and considering for a system with intramolecular interaction, the existence of the equilibria

$$Cu(L) + Cu(L) \rightleftharpoons ([Cu(L)_2]_{op.} + [Cu(L)_2]_{cl.}) + Cu^{2+} \quad (14)$$

$$10^{\Delta \log K_{Cu}(expt.)}$$

$$= ([Cu(L)_2]_{op.} + [Cu(L)_2]_{cl.}) [Cu] / ([Cu(L)][Cu(L)])$$

and for a system without intramolecular interaction, the equilibria,

$$Cu(L) + Cu(L) \rightleftharpoons [Cu(L)_2]_{op.} + Cu^{2+} \quad (15)$$

$$10^{\log K_{Cu}(op.)}$$

$$= ([Cu(L)_2]_{op.} [Cu]) / ([Cu(L)][Cu(L)])$$

so that

$$K_I = [10^{\Delta \log K_{Cu}(expt.)} / 10^{\log K_{Cu}(op.)}] - 1 \quad (16)$$

where,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{expt.})} = \log K_{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{op.}) + \text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{cl.})]}^{\text{Cu}} - 2 \log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{op.})} = \log K_{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]_{\text{op.}}}^{\text{Cu}} - 2 \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (18)$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{expt.})} - \Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{op.})} = \log (K_1 + 1) \quad (19)$$

$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{expt.})}$ and $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}/(\text{op.})}$ values were calculated by taking

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{expt.})}^{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{op.}) + \text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{cl.})]}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (20)$$

and tentatively assuming,

$$\log K_{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]_{\text{op.}}}^{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})_2}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (21)$$

where, $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})_2}^{\text{Cu}}$ stands for the statistically calculated value^{18,19} of stability constant of 1:2 Cu^{II} -BSA complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{LH})_2$, if there be any, having an identical disposition of ligand sites but devoid of intramolecular hydrophobic interactions. The magnitude of K_1 (Table 1) indicated that nearly more than 90% of the $\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2^{\text{Cu}}$ complex was present in the closed form (XII).

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References

1. H. SIGEL and B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 385.
2. U. SCHELLER-KRATTIGER, K. H. SCHELLER and R. B. MARTIN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta* 1982, **60**, 45.
3. G. K. HUGHES and F. LIONS, *J. Proc. R. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1938, **71**, 209 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1938, **32**, 5680).
4. Y. KANAOKA, T. SEKINE, M. MACHIDA, Y. SOMA, K. TANIZAMA and Y. BAN, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1964, **12**, 127 (*Chem. Abs'r.*, 1964, **6'**, 15856).
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 3rd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1975, Vol. I, pp. 183-202, 291-276, 406.
6. A. I. VOGEL in "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", E. L. B. S., London, 1958, p. 167.
7. G. N. MUKHERJEE and P. K. CHAKRABORTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 841.
8. L. G. VAN UITERT, C. G. HASS, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. E. DOGLUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 455, 2739, 8597, 8862.
9. H. M. IRVING, M. G. MILLS and L. D. PETTIT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1967, **38**, 475.
10. J. LURIE, "Hand Book of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1978, p. 198.
11. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397.
12. V. D. KHANOLKAR, D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 931.
13. T. TOMITA, E. KYUNO and R. TSUCHIYA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1968, **41**, 1130.
14. H. REINERT and R. WEISS, *Hoppe-Sey'er's Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1969, **3** 0, 1310.
15. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
16. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 256.
17. A. E. MARTELL, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **17**, 129.
18. B. SEN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **27**, 515.
19. V. S. SHARMA and J. SCHUBERT, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1969, **46** 506.
20. B. E. FISCHER and H. SIGEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 2998.
21. H. SIGEL, B. E. FISCHER and E. FARKAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 925.